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Research Article

THE EFFECT OF WATER PAINTING ON CREATIVITY AND SOCIAL ADJUSTMENT OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Fatemeh Baneshi¹ and Dr.Hossein Aflakifard^{*2}

¹Department of Psychology, Marvdasht Branch, Islamic Azad University, Marvdasht, Iran

^{*2}Assistant professor, Department of Educational Sciences, Farhangian University, Iran

Abstract:

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the effect of water painting on creativity and social adjustment of students. This research was applied in terms of its nature and purpose. Semi-experimental method was used with pre-test and post-test, and control and control groups. The population of the study consisted of all primary school girl students in Marvdasht who were studying in the academic year 2015-2016. Using a multi-stage cluster sampling method, 40 people were selected as the statistical sample. In order to collect information, Child Behavioral Questionnaire (CBCL) and Torrance Creative Thinking Test Questionnaire (visual form B) were used. Data were analyzed using covariance analysis method. Results showed that painting with water had a positive and significant effect on creativity and social compatibility of primary school students.

Keywords: Creativity, Social Adaptation, Water Painting

Corresponding author:

Dr.Hossein Aflakifard,

Assistant professor,

Department of Educational Sciences,

Farhangian, University, Iran

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Childhood has a crucial role to play in human life, and every experience that a child acquires will widen her vision and grow her brain, the breadth of the childhood, which has gained more experience in different ways, is more complete than vision. A child living in a sedentary environment. The child fairly soon realizes that the drawing of a painting is an expression of expression that matches his thoughts, and he releases his imagination and at the same time provides him with great pleasure. Art has a broad and mysterious concept of definition of art, heavenly and subjective, such as having good feelings and thoughts, loving to be loving beauty, enjoying serving others [1]. Painting is a free language of the child. The child, when performing artistic activity, abandoned himself from the prohibitions and reached peace. Today, most scholars and researchers believe that the basis of human power is due to its creativity, then it can be said that history is the result of recording the creative abilities of mankind. Nowadays, all societies are in urgent need of creativity. Creativity is the key to progress and to prevent a dynamic alliance. The creativity of the passage is glittering towards a brighter future, and is the basis of most of human well-being in the individual and social life of the present and the future [2]. In fact, about half a century ago, creativity has become one of the basic issues of scientific psychology, as well as a researched and educated topic. In 1950, Guilford at the Congress of Psychologists of America said: "Creativity should not be an exceptional gift that exists only in some people, but it should be understood that creativity is more or less available in all individuals and ages." [3]. Painting and design are one of the most important factors in expressing the intentions and thoughts, beliefs and inner needs of mankind, which has long been used by human beings. Engaging in this creative activity, including the creation of painting, or the application and use of it, can, in addition to developing the sense of the beauty of friendship and human virtue, have an effective role in the development of personality, the recognition of its problems and psychological disorders [4]. There are plenty of ways and means of nurturing a child, one of

RESULTS:**Table 1: Reliability coefficients of creativity test by Cronbach's alpha**

Total creativity	Flexibility component	Fluid component	Component expansion	Ingredient component	Different parts of the creativity test
0.84	0.78	0.82	0.91	0.89	Reliability coefficients

which is less attention, but more than anything else can help educate the child (painting). The color and the image more than anything else will notice the mind, and at the same time it is a device that the child can create before it can. It is enough to grasp the color and image of the eye, and it is enough for the child to create the color of the hand and to put it on the wall or on whatever the tail of his hand, even on his face and clothing. If painting is not the deepest means of teaching children, one can say that it is one of the most important and the first means of education. Nevertheless, in our educational system, especially in the elementary period, it is considered less than anything else, and if We want to argue that painting at all stages of life, even at high ages, can be an effective means of human excellence, and it can be argued that it is an effective means for mental education and intellectual development, but, like any science or other technique Knowledge of the way to use it [5]. According to the above, the purpose of the present research is to impart water painting on creativity and social adjustment.

RESEARCH METHOD:

This research was done according to the purpose and nature of the application which was done by semi-experimental method with pre-test and post-test run with the control group.

Statistical Society:

Includes all first-year elementary girl students in public and primary schools of Marvdasht, who were studying in the academic year 2015-2016.

Sample and Sampling Method:

A randomized cluster sampling method was used to select 40 students as the sample. Firstly, from among elementary schools of Marvdasht girls, they randomly selected a school, and then two classes were randomly selected and randomly selected. One class (20 people) was selected as the experimental group and one class (20 people) as the control group.

Research tool:

In this research, Child Behavioral Logbook (CBCL) and Torrance Creative Thinking Test Questionnaire (Image Form B) were used.

After conducting the pre-test, the first painting session was conducted by establishing emotional relationships with the students and discussing the number of meetings and activities of each session. In each training session, which lasted 45 minutes, and its implementation method taken from the instructions given in the Art Education Guide for elementary school children, as well as using experimental methods and consulting with students, this technique was planned. First, the final session was summed up and then summed up. During the

hearings, the verbal and non-verbal encouragement was followed. At the end of nine sessions, the Torrance Creativity Test was again held and the parents completed the Behavioral Logbook questionnaire, completed as a post-test both groups were tested and controlled.

Data analysis method:

Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean) and inferential statistics (covariance analysis) were used to analyze the data.

Table 2: mean, standard deviation, test group score in pre-test and post-test

Standard deviation	average	Abundance	Test variable	
13.81	81.40	20	pre-exam	Creativity
14.80	93.75	20	Post-test	
11.25	66.60	20	pre-exam	Compatibility
12.27	87.85	20	Post-test	

Table 3: mean, standard deviation, test group score in pre-test and post-test

Standard deviation	Average	Abundance	Control group variable	
13.45	81.10	20	pre-exam	Creativity
13.77	81.15	20	Post-test	
11.19	64.70	20	pre-exam	Compatibility
11.45	64.05	20	Post-test	

First hypothesis: Water painting on students' creativity has a meaningful effect?

Table 4: Levine test to determine the equality of variances

Levine test (equality of variances)		Test	Component
Sig	F		
0.39	0.746	Assuming the equality of variances	
		Assuming that the variances are not uniform	

Table 5: Results of covariance of painting with water on creativity

Partial squat	sig	f	MS	df	Sum of squares	Source of change
0.95	0.000	703.88	7382.24	1	7382.24	pre-exam
0.79	0.000	144.07	1511.07	1	1511.07	Difference between groups
----	-----	-----	10.488	37	388.052	Error
----	-----	-----	-----	40	315258	Total

Second hypothesis: Water painting on student social adjustment has a meaningful effect?**Table 6: Levine test to determine the equality of variances**

Levine test (equality of variances)		Test	Component
Sig	F		
0.35	0.87	Assuming the equality of variances	
		Assuming that the variances are not uniform	

Table 7: Results of covariance analysis of water painting on social adjustment

Partial squat	sig	f	MS	df	Sum of squares	Source of change
0.93	0.000	512.63	4991.25	1	4991.25	pre-exam
0.92	0.000	487.15	4743.16	1	4743.16	Difference between groups
----	-----	-----	9.73	37	360.25	Error
----	-----	-----	-----	40	241752	Total

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

In this section, according to the results of the data analysis, all the research hypotheses are examined.

First hypothesis: Water painting on students' creativity has a meaningful effect?

To test this assumption, the statistical method of covariance analysis was used. Results show that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest groups.

In other words, there is a significant difference between the experimental post-test creativity of the experimental group and the control group, given the mean value that creativity has increased. The confirmation of this hypothesis in line with the researches of Sohrabi et al.[6-9]. This result, given the type of activity that was done, can be believed, with the views of Soborn (1996) and Torrance (1990), that both individuals can more and more be creative, and cultivate intellectual abilities, the foundation of creativity is. During his 15-year experience in studying creative thinking, Torrens has seen evidence that creativity can be trained. Osborne also believes that creativity can be blurred by utilization, or by developing imaginative exercises that develop creativity in individuals (Osborne, Ghasemzadeh translation, 1992). Expressive creativity is like children's spontaneous drawing. This result, given the type of activity that was done, can be believed, with the views of Soborn (1996) and Torrance (1990), that both individuals can more and more be creative, and cultivate intellectual abilities, the foundation of creativity is. During his 15-year experience in studying creative thinking, Torrens has seen evidence that creativity can be trained. Osborne also believes that creativity

can be blurred by utilization, or by developing imaginative exercises that develop creativity in individuals (Osborne, Ghasemzadeh translation, 1992). Expressive creativity is like children's spontaneous drawing. The essence of life is creative. Because it organizes itself and is constantly innovating. In the meantime, humans are unmatched, because they create an artistic or practical piece of data. Man has the ability to create his own regulatory models. Creativity is a mental capability that is developing in the child. On the other hand, the child is very curious and looking at the age of the elementary school. The child regularly reviews his mental knowledge, sometimes changes them, and occasionally something new from the heart. Kids, and these innovations are the brainchild of his imaginative and explorer, and painting is one of the best ways a child can transfer his mind to others. In this activity, the atmosphere has been created where the child passes what he gets into his mind.

In explaining this finding, it can be said that there is, in fact, a possibility of creativity growth that has prepared its own subterranean mind that water-based painting for children has a new experience that underpins the child's mind because of the different form of painting and happiness by creating a new environment. And the freedom to collect new ideas and compare them and their new formation as a source of creativity, as well as to expand new experiences for children's artistic activities and to be comfortable with expressing their ideas. Enabling their imagination and allowing them to experience new and more free classroom environments Of their own language.

Second hypothesis: Water painting on student social adjustment has a meaningful effect?

To test this assumption, we use the statistical method of covariance analysis which shows that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest groups.

In other words, there is a significant difference between the experimental post-test scores of the experimental group and the control group, considering the average amount of creativity. The confirmation of this hypothesis is in line with Orit and Hamilton (2003), Van List (2001), Sadeghi Sayyah (2011).

And is inconsistent with the Rahsepar research (2015), which can be caused by several factors such as the duration of the project, the method of implementation, the different cultures in the two places, the age of the experiment group, or the overall nature of the painting with water. Conclusion Based on the nature of the project, according to Welsh and Karen (2001), human behavior is influenced by social factors, and if human personality develops to the extent that there is an appropriate interaction and exchange between him and the environment. Social pressures have a great influence on individual behavior and, on the other hand, human being has a flexible existence. He not only adapts to the environment, but also changes the environment according to his own will. Erickson, who views the game as a way of thinking about difficult experiences reinforcing a sense of mastery, uses this arguing in the arts so children can get a satisfying painting.

Children depict their emotions and motivations in their drawings. Using painting for character evaluation and psychological adjustment forms part of the wider use of diffuse methods in clinical psychology and psychiatry. In explaining this finding it can be said that by painting with water the child's happiness and vitality will be left out of the problems and problems that he has left and can express his excitement and motivation in his paintings, as well as the disturbing thoughts isolated And they all focus on the story, drawing and coloring, which is something pleasant and useful for them, it creates a calmness that creates new thoughts that sometimes make changes in order to be in harmony with the environment. And sometimes can find ways to change the environment as desired, and establish a better relationship with each other. Finally increased compatibility in them.

REFERENCES:

1. Khosh Konesh, Abolghasem (2006). "Art Therapy Definition, History, Methodology and Measurement". Congress of Art Therapy in Iran.
2. Hosseini, Afzal-al-Sadat (1999). The Creativity and its Methods of Breeding. To publish, Astan Quds Razavi Publication.
3. Haghghi, Jamal Behroozi, Naser Shokrkon Hossein and Mehrabi Zadeh ArHonarmand, Mahnaz (2003). Comparison of nine combinations of intelligence and creativity in terms of personality traits in the first year high school students in Ahwaz. Educational Sciences and Psychology 82-59, 10.3.
4. Mirza Beigi, Ali (2003). The Art of Education in Children's Mental Health Education. Tehran: School Publications.
5. Dadashzadeh, Kaveh (1994). Paintings and Children's Writings, Kottenberg Publications, First Edition.
6. Sohrabi, Fariba and Shanni Yalahagh, Maliheh and Shokrshekan, Hussein (2005). The Effect of Brain Instruction on the Creativity of Shahid Chamran University Students in Ahwaz with Control of Intelligence, Education Sciences and Psychology of Ahwaz.
7. Sharifi Sorki, Arezoo (2006). How to look at your child's painting, Society Psychology, No. 36, 42-44.
8. Araghiyeh, Alireza Siadat, Behjat Sadat and Khorshidi, Abbas and Mirzamani Bafghi, Seyyed Mahmoud (2011). Effect of Art Education on the creativity of elementary school students in Islamshahr. Consultation and Psychotherapy.
9. Shaukatpour, Shahla Maghsod, Faghir Pood and Seyyedeh Khadijeh Jamali (2013) The Effect of Painting Methods on the Creativity and Self-Retaining of Children ", The First International Conference on Psychology and Behavioral Sciences, Tehran, Tehran, Iran.
10. Nejad Pilehrood, Farahnaz (2006). A case study of curative art therapy with a pediatric-based therapeutic approach with delayed development of a master's thesis. "Congress of Art Therapy in Iran.
11. Rahsepar, Fatemeh (2015). Effect of teaching painting art on decreasing the amount of anxiety and increasing social compatibility of female students. Master's thesis of Islamic Azad University, Marvdasht, Faculty of Educational Sciences